

**THE IMPACT OF USING DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL GAMES
TEACHING HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN
LANGUAGE**

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Abstract: This article analyses how digital educational games can enhance teaching English as a foreign language to high school students. Two methods of qualitative research were used observation and informal interviews during specific lessons. A grade 8 class was used during the observation and informal interview lessons. This study was conducted without the student's prior knowledge of this study. Various games within 'Wordwall' were used. Based on the observation during the observational lessons, it was established that these digital educational games should be incorporated into English as a foreign language (EFL) lessons. Changing the games regularly increases the productivity of the students and keeps them engaged. There was increased participation, and a good sense of competitiveness and learning was created whilst having fun.

Keywords: digital educational games, Wordwall, English as a foreign language (EFL), differentiation, critical thinking

**ВЛИЯНИЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ОБУЧАЮЩИХ ИГР НА ОБУЧЕНИЕ
СТАРШЕКЛАССНИКОВ АНГЛИЙСКОМУ ЯЗЫКУ КАК
ИНОСТРАННОМУ**

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Аннотация: В этой статье анализируется, как цифровые обучающие игры могут улучшить преподавание английского языка старшеклассникам как иностранного. На определенных занятиях были использованы два метода качественного исследования - наблюдение и неформальные интервью. На уроках наблюдения и неформальных интервью был использован 8 класс. Это исследование было проведено без предварительного уведомления студента об этом исследовании. Были использованы различные игры в "Wordwall". На основе наблюдений, проведенных во время контрольных занятий, было установлено, что эти цифровые обучающие игры должны быть включены в уроки английского языка как иностранного (EFL). Регулярная смена игр повышает продуктивность учащихся и поддерживает их вовлеченность. Наблюдалась высокая активность и положительное чувство конкуренции, а также возможности учиться в веселой обстановке.

Ключевые слова: цифровые обучающие игры, Wordwall, английский как иностранный язык (EFL), дифференциация, критическое мышление.

**RAQAMLI TA'LIMIY O'YINLARNING YUQORI SINIF
O'QUVCHILARIGA INGLIZ TILINI CHET TILI SIFATIDA
O'RGATISHGA TA'SIRI**

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola raqamli ta'limiy o'yinlarning o'rta maktab o'quvchilariga ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitish jarayonida samaradorlikni oshirishga qanday ta'sir qilishini tahlil qiladi. Sifatli tadqiqotning ikki usuli-ma'lum darslar davomida o'tkazilgan kuzatuv va norasmiy suhbatlardan foydalangan. Kuzatuv va norasmiy suhbat darslari 8-sinf o'quvchilari ishtirokidan foydalanilgan. Ushbu tadqiqotda o'quvchilar ushbu mavzuda oldindan bilimga ega emasligini hisobga olgan holda o'tkazilgan. Tadqiqot davomida "Wordwall" platformasidagi turli xil o'yinlar foydalanilgan. Kuzatuv darslari davomida aniqlanishicha, bunday raqamli ta'limiy o'yinlarni ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitish (EFL) darslariga kiritish kerak. O'yinlarning muntazam ravishda almashtirib turilishi o'quvchilarning mahsuldorligini oshiradi va ularni darsga jalb qiladi. O'yin davomida ishtirok faolligi oshib, o'quv jarayoniga raqobat ruhini va zavqni olib keldi.

Kalit so'zlar: raqamli ta'limga doir o'yinlar, Wordwall, ingliz tili chet tili sifatida (EFL), farqlash, tanqidiy fikrlash

1. Introduction: According to [Fomenko, 2021] English is the most common language spoken in the world and it is the language used in the international business world. Thus, it is important to learn English. The evolution of technology has changed the way teaching should be approached to ensure effective teaching for EFL students. According to [Horsley, 2024]

technology has transformed the digital classroom environment into a more interactive learning environment with the use of digital educational games whilst teaching EFL students. In most cases English is not commonly spoken in certain countries and with the use of technology in a classroom or learning centres, technology makes learning more interesting, and accessible, keeps the students engaged and motivated as well as improves their English skills. [Horsley, 2024] also states that the students were born into a digital age and therefore they respond better to more modern techniques of teaching and learning and performance increases where interactive technology is used.

In this study conducted with the 8A class, the objective was to see the effectiveness of learning EFL when playing digital educational games and whether the goal would be reached. Digital educational games such as Wordwall were used as it has a variety of activities to keep the students engaged and create a form of competitiveness. The goal was to see if students would retain the information they had learned during this interactive lesson, how involved the students would be during the lesson and whether were they having fun but at the same time were they learning English. This was an extremely important study as this would determine the way teachers could improve student engagement and alter their way of teaching to accommodate the modern student. Learning should not be seen as a punishment, but rather a fun and engaging way to gain new knowledge and implement the newly learnt language in the world. The result of this study indicated that 85% of students participated in these games compared to the 60% engagement during traditional class. Digital educational games had a positive effect on EFL students' engagement, knowledge retention and motivation. A week after this lesson was conducted, the students wanted to play the games again proving this interactive way of teaching creates excitement for the students and makes learning more fun.

Literature Review: According to [Deesri, 2002] the primary focus of digital educational games in the classroom is to help the students achieve their necessary goal of learning EFL whilst at the same time having fun. In other words, the students are learning without realising it. [Akma Adi Kasuma, 2017] states that we are currently facing a digital progression and the use of technology in the classroom has become popular, which leads to engaging activities, effective reflection and positive collaboration. Moreover [Wu & Huang, 2017] states that memorising EFL vocabulary is mundane, difficult and stressful. Increased learning motivation and interest developed due to the use of digital educational games in the classroom. Playing is essential to the development of a child according to [Mayyas, 2022] and it has a positive effect on high school students learning EFL. It is not only effective for the students but with the help of digital technology, it allows educators to expand their knowledge and skills and to 'change things up' in the classroom, thus moving away from traditional methods.

Digital educational games should be aimed at the specific skill targeted during the lesson whether it be reading, writing, speaking or listening. These games should target the different levels of English within the class and thus relate to differentiation. Games encourage students to interact socially, and compete against each other in a friendly way and help with the retainment of knowledge [Sabir, 2021]. Games emphasise the meaning of EFL learning, students will remember the language, topic or vocabulary they have learnt. It is fun, interesting and different which creates significant advantages when learning EFL with minimal effort [Tuan, 2010].

As one can see based on the above review, digital educational games have a positive effect on students and teachers, it creates a positive environment. As with anything in life, there needs to be structure when using these games. One cannot just put on a game and let the students play. There needs to be an end goal.

[Shapiro, 2015] states that digital educational games cannot be successful when one uses them as a reward. It should form part of the class as it plays a crucial part in developing critical thinking and learning. To assign students roles requires everyone to be involved and gives them a sense of belonging as well as decreases altercations due to lack of clarity and instructions. Optimal discipline is required when playing games in an EFL class. The students need to know the rules of the game as well as what is expected of them. Reward the students who follow the rules during the game and when they get the correct answer [Focal Point EdTech Lda, 2024]The educator should just facilitate the game and allow the students to take control within the spectrum of the rules provided.

Digital educational games are child-centred and develop skills the students need when leaving school [Perrotta, 2013]. The author is in view that digital educational games would have a more positive effect on teaching high school EFL classes due to the positivity and excitement the students experience. However, one cannot just use games in the class. The lessons need to be structured with every activity designed for a reason and with a specific outcome. If you repeat the same type of games constantly the students will get bored and not show any interest. Differentiating between teaching techniques constantly should keep students motivated and engaged [TEFL Academy, 2024].

To summarise, the digital games educators play with students have many advantages in an EFL classroom if it is done with the right intention and correct classroom management.

Research Methodology: There were 32 participants during this blind study, 16 females and 16 males aged 13 to 14 years of age in a public school in Uzbekistan. The student's level of English ranges between A2 and B1 level. These high school students participated in a lesson where various digital educational games were introduced to them unaware of the study as it could

influence the purpose and results, in which the author was the educator conducting the blind study.

The resources used were an electronic board and a website called 'Wordwall'. 'Wordwall is a digital platform where various EFL topics are covered in the form of games. During the lesson observation was conducted in the following areas: Participation, motivation and retainment of knowledge, other changes within the class were also observed. At the end of the lesson, a general discussion took place in which the students gave their opinions as well as suggestions on how to improve the lesson to ensure optimal learning occurs. Preference was also given to the types of games that were used during this blind study.

Analysis and Results: 'Wordwall' is a multipurpose website used to enrich and create a different atmosphere in the class whilst learning EFL. One can use pre-existing templates or create individual games based on the textbook used in school. Below in Fig. 1.1 are all the different types of games one can use.

<https://wordwall.net/>

The first game I used is called “Spin the wheel” Fig 1.2, one student nominates themselves and clicks the button to spin the wheel. That student should then answer the question. After answering the question, the student can nominate another student, that will follow the same routine. At first, the students were shy to speak, but after a couple of them spoke, more students got involved. All 32 students spun the wheel and had a turn to speak. This observation concluded that speaking participation was 100%, the students helped each other, translated some words or questions and corrected each other’s speech and grammar all whilst having fun. This can be used as an icebreaker at the beginning of a lesson or a short exercise during the lesson. One cannot simply do this for 45 minutes straight as the ‘novelty’ wears off and the students start losing interest. Hence one should always differentiate between games and topics.

Fig 1.2

Spin the wheel

‘Matching Pairs’ Fig
memory game where you

1.3 is a

need to match two of the same object or meaning. This encourages concentration but can also help with topics in grammar such as homophones, homonyms, synonyms, antonyms and more. Before starting the game one needs to explain the topic and what is expected of them. Students took turns to turn 2 cards and try to match them. After each match, they had to explain the meaning of the words. As observed before, some students were sceptical and did not want to participate, but when they saw a large group of students having fun, helping each other and the positivity surrounding this activity, they joined in. There were about 50% of the students would get up and pair the cards, but the other students would provide instructions and guidance and where they could find the pairs. It was observed that about 80% of the students participated in this activity. A noticeable observation was that the students stopped playing on their mobile phones or doing homework for other subjects and tried to get involved. They also started to give instructions in English instead of speaking Uzbek or Russian, which was already a victory itself. It also became a class competition, as the game was timed, the students tried to complete each activity faster than the previous one but still concentrated on accuracy. With each activity they completed their time was decreased. The first activity was completed in 8 minutes comprising 12 tiles that needed to be flipped. At the end of this activity, they managed to flip 24 tiles in 5 minutes. A maximum of 4 of this activity can be done depending on the number of tiles. After this, the students become less engaged and lose interest.

Fig 1.3

Matching Pairs - Synonyms

'Unjumble' Fig 1.4 is a great tool for students to learn sentence structures. This helps the students in grammar and improves their writing skills. The topic of simple past and simple continuous was chosen. On the board, a sentence will appear, and the students have to drag the words in the correct order. The games give them a point for every word placed in the correct space, but if they can do it in a certain number of moves, they will score additional points. 65% of the students participated from the beginning. Based on the author's observation, students just started to unjumble the sentence, without realising that they could score additional points by planning. This activity tested not only their knowledge but also their critical thinking skills. Some students even wrote the sentence down to unjumble it before they attempted it on the board. To make things more competitive the class was divided into groups of 3-4 students. Each group had 1 minute to write down the correct sentence. After which each group had a turn to complete the sentence on the board. They gave themselves 1 point for each word that was placed in the correct order. For the bonus points, they only scored the bonus points when it was that group's turn to answer on the board and if they unjumbled the sentence within the specific moves. It was ensured that all the students had the same number of questions and turned on the board.

The students enjoyed this activity as it forced them to think critically, have fun and compete against each other. Since they were placed in groups it was observed that all the students got involved in the game and within each group the students started to assign different roles to each other with no interference from the educator. As soon as a student became disinterested the other group members

would ensure that student and complete cooperation would ensue. The students motivated each other within their group.

Fig 1.4

Unjumble Simple past and – Continuous

At the end of the observation and activities, a general informal review discussion was conducted. There was a mutual feeling amongst all members of the class that they enjoyed the interactive lesson and that they would want more lessons like this in the future. They also stated that some activities were more difficult than others, but once they grasped the concept it became easier. They felt empowered and encouraged whilst doing the activities as they received help from their peers. The games were more effective when it was constantly changed as they got bored by repeating the same activity and felt it wasn't challenging anymore. The most fascinating observation was that all the males participated in all the activities and games, it was the females that got distracted and needed encouragement from their peers.

At the beginning of the lessons, the students were asked what they could remember from the previous lesson and almost 80% of the students did not know.

After 1 week a review lesson was conducted about the same topics that were covered during the blind observation. A significant change was seen in knowledge retention and critical thinking. 70% of the students could recall the type and topic of games that were played. They could recall the structure of the grammar topics that were covered and give examples thereof. 40% of the students could even recall some funny moments they experienced during the lessons.

Conclusion and Recommendations: Based on the observation and informal interview, one could safely say that games play an integral part in developing EFL in the classroom. The students are more active, different skills are being developed and knowledge retainment increased. The students were learning actively whilst having fun. They did not realise that they were learning and thought they had a free lesson where no work was being done.

Differentiation in teaching methods is vital to effective EFL teaching. It empowers the students to gain confidence in a Foreign Language, it makes the lessons interesting, and it moves away from traditional teaching methods. The most important thing to remember is the fact that digital educational games cannot be used on their own or replace other teaching methods. Instead, it can be used to enhance and supplement the teaching dynamics in the class and thus contribute positively towards EFL education. With technology becoming more and more popular, based on these results, one should encourage educators to be more creative in teaching and positively use technology to reinforce knowledge, where possible.

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